

Excel line number:

Case No:

Tweet ID

Times retweeted

Date

Time

Gender

01 Male

02 Female

03 Other

04 Unidentified

Suspended account?

01 Yes

02 No

Religion

01 Christian

02 Muslim

03 Hindu

04 Sikh

05 Buddhist

06 Jewish

07 Other

08 Atheist

99 Unidentified

Deleted/unavailable tweet?

01 Yes

02 No

Tweet type

01 Original tweet

02 Retweet

03 Quote tweet

04 Reply

Position on Muslims/Islam

01 Anti-Muslim

02 Supports Muslims

03 Mixed

04 Neutral/no view

[If Quote tweet] **Response to original tweet**

01 Agreement/endorsement

02 Disagreement

03 Mixed/qualification

04 Other

99 N/A

Affiliation

- 01 Individual
- 02 State Institution/ Politician/Party
- 03 Leftist or Social justice advocacy groups
- 04 Alt/Far right group
- 05 Mainstream media organisation / journalist
- 06 Blogger/ alternative media organisation / journalist
- 07 Independent political analyst/commentator/author
- 08 NGO
- 09 Celebrity
- 10 Parody account
- 11 Academic
- 12 Mixed
- 13 Pressure group
- 14 Charity
- 15 Artist/Musician
- 16 Religious Representative
- 98 Other
- 99 Unidentified

Location

- 01 UK
- 02 US/ North America
- 03 Europe
- 04 India
- 05 Pakistan
- 06 Bangladesh
- 07 Other Asian countries
- 08 MENA region
- 09 Other African countries
- 10 Australasia/Oceania
- 11 South/Central America
- 12 Russia
- 13 Mixed (two or more locations are mentioned)
- 98 Other
- 99 None mentioned

Topic 1 & 2

01 Anti-Muslim, general ('Muslims are [negative trait]')

02 Anti-Muslim, specific (extremism, evil, radicalisation, anti-Quran, anti-Islamic scripture etc)

03 Islamist Terrorism

04 Islamification/ spread of Islam (Cultural clash, censorship, Islam taking over the world, conversion, attacks on 'our' culture, country, Shariah law, references to the movement of refugees, Muslim problem, cultural deviance)

05 Muslims scapegoated for Coronavirus (including not following restrictions)

06 Changes/ disruption to Muslims' practices, celebrations due to Covid/ Covid measures affecting this

07 Islamophobia is denied/exaggerated/playing the victim

08 Disputing that Covid is spread by Muslims

09 Public information tweets/ Instructions (add scientific breakthroughs to this that are not Muslim related which will go in 12)

10 The impact and spread of Covid (specifically funerals and reporting the death toll and spread of Coronavirus in terms of volume)

11 Pro-Muslim, general ('Muslims are [positive trait]')

12 Pro-Muslim, specific (contribution to society, acts of kindness, religion of peace, etc)

13 Anti-Muslim discrimination/racism/ Islamophobia/ attacks on Muslims

14. Anti-Hindu propaganda

15 Covid heroes (Medical and other emergency staff otherwise goes in 12 or non-Muslim?)

16 Covid victims (Profiles of victims)

17 Expressions of faith/prayers

18 Muslim celebrations (other than disruption/ changes to which should be coded as 06)

19 Coronavirus and British politics

20 Coronavirus and US politics

21 Coronavirus and Indian politics

22 Coronavirus and global politics

23 International relations

24 Politics, general/other

25 Pro conservative/right agendas

26 Anti conservative/right agendas

27 Pro liberal/ left agendas

28 Anti liberal/ left agendas / anti 'woke'

29 Immigration/deportation

30 Community relations/cohesion

31 Protest

32 Commentary on anti-Muslim propaganda including the media

33 Right-wing criticism of mainstream media

34 Tweet disseminates/premised on conspiracy theory

35 Tweet identifies/alleges conspiracy theory

36 accusation of antisemitism

37 antisemitism in content

99 Other

Hashtags – only coding content of tweet	31	eid2020
Hashtag 1	32	eidaladha
Hashtag 2	33	eidaladha2020
Hashtag 3	34	eidaladha2020mubarak
	35	eidalfitr
	36	eidathome
	37	eidmubarak
1 none	38	eidmubarak2020
2 other	39	eiduladha
3 à¤®	40	eidulfitr
4 à¤•	41	fakenews
5 adhan	42	granada
6 ahmadiyya	43	gujarat
7 altnewsfactcheck	44	hajj
8 amitshah	45	hajj2020
9 awaninews	46	hapus covid19
10 babrimasjid	47	hindu
11 corona	48	humanityfirst
12 coronafreepakistan	49	india
13 coronajihad	50	indiafightscorona
14 coronaupdatesinindia	51	iran
15 coronavirus	52	islam
16 coronavirusoutbreak	53	islamandpatriotism
17 coronaviruspandemic	54	islamophobia
18 coronavirusupdate	55	islamophobia_in_india
19 covid	56	jantacurfew
20 covid__19	57	lasg
21 covid_19	58	lka
22 covid_19india	59	loc
23 covid19	60	lockdown
24 covid19malaysia	61	lockdown21
25 covid19nigeria	62	lockdown4
26 covid19uk	63	lockdown4guidelines
27 covid2019	64	lockdownindia
28 covidã¸19	65	mosque
	66	mosques
30 eid	67	muslim

68	muslimgenocide	Image(s)? [in original content]
69	muslims	01 Yes
70	muslimsaviours	
71	nayahindustan	02 No
72	nayakashmir	
73	nizamuddin	
74	nizamuddinmarkaz	Icons/Emojis? [in original content]
75	onenation	01 Yes
76	pakistan	02 No
77	palestine	
78	pandemic	
79	peace	URL? [in Quoted content]
80	ramadan	01 Yes
81	saudiarabia	02 No
82	social	
83	socialdistancing	03 N/A
84	sopstosustainsuccess	04 Unknown
85	spain	
86	stayhome	
87	staysafe	Image(s)? [in Quoted content]
88	staysafestayhealthy	01 Yes
89	Stopcovidislamophobia	02 No
90	tablighijamaat	03 N/A
91	{1, None}...	04 Unknown
92	uklockdown	
93	watch	
94	yemen	
95	zaareen	Icons/Emojis? [in Quoted content]
	URL? [in original content]	01 Yes
01 Yes		02 No
02 No		03 N/A
		04 Unknown